

2 **Assessment of heat transfer mechanisms of a novel high-frequency** 3 **inductive power transformer and coupled simulation using FEA.**

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9 **Abstract:** The calculation of the temperature fields in solid state transformers is a critical step of the design process
10 in order to ensure the stable and efficient operation of the device. Transformers operating in high frequencies can
11 develop increased temperatures that potentially may result in the failure of the components due to the associated
12 thermal stresses. This paper investigates the heat transfer mechanisms of a novel inductive power transfer (IPT)
13 system submerged in a dielectric oil and operating at 50 kHz, in the context of SSTAR, a Horizon Europe project. A
14 two-way coupled electromagnetic-thermal finite element simulation model is established using the commercial
15 software ANSYS. The model is later used to calculate the temperature field of the IPT components based on the
16 electromagnetic losses. Finally, a parametric analysis is conducted to assess the effect of the operating frequency and
17 the dielectric gap on the produced heat. The results indicate the increased temperature levels, in the order of 220 °C,
18 the uniform temperature distribution and finally they highlight the need to include a cooling system in the layout.

19 **Keywords:** Inductive Power Transfer, Thermal Simulation, Electromagnetic-thermal Model, Heat Transfer
20 Mechanisms, Finite Element Analysis

21 **Highlights**

- 22 • Design of a novel high frequency 50kHz Inductive Power Transfer system
- 23 • Assessment of the heat transfer mechanism of an Inductive Power Transfer system
- 24 • Development of a comprehensive coupled electromagnetic-thermal simulation model
- 25 • Parametric analysis on the effect of frequency and dielectric gap on power loss and temperature

26 **1 Introduction**

27 1.1 Energy transition

28 Electricity is considered to account for about 20% of the worldwide total final consumption of energy and its
29 importance is paramount for a variety of applications, ranging from industry to residential buildings and electric
30 mobility [1]. In more detail, according to [1], in 2021 the electricity sector accounted for 59% of the global use of
31 coal and 34% of the global use of natural gas. As a result, it was responsible for over one-third of energy-related CO₂
32 emissions in the same year. Evidently, the energy mix of the electricity sector has raised concerns, highlighting the
33 necessity of the ongoing energy transition [2]. For example, the European Union (EU) aims to have an economy with
34 net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050, which is an objective of the European Green Deal [3]. In order to achieve
35 such targets, Renewable Energy Sources (RES), e.g. solar panels, Wind Farms (WF) and hydroelectric power plants,
36 as well as storage systems are gradually incorporated into the power network, substituting conventional sources, such
37 as generators. Indicatively, in 2021 Iceland, Norway and Sweden had a high share of final energy consumption
38 originating from RES, ranging from 60% up to 80% [4], while the same value for all other EU countries was below
39 50%, resulting in an overall share equal to 21.8% [5]. It should be noted that solar energy is the sort which is growing
40 at the highest pace in the EU. More specifically, in 2021, the respective market grew by 1,825.7 GW, while 5.7% of
41 EU's total electricity production came from solar energy [6]. Its popularity is attributed to the fact that it is modular

42 and flexible and can be installed both in large open areas, constituting a solar plant, or individually on rooftops of
43 buildings, enhancing their autonomy in a sustainable way [7].

44 Regarding the technical incorporation of RES in the energy mix, most RES are installed in the Medium Voltage
45 (MV) and Low Voltage (LV) distribution networks [8]. Also, in many cases, their installation is accompanied by the
46 installation of a storage system, e.g., a Battery Energy Storage System (BESS), a supercapacitor or a flywheel,
47 capable of storing the surplus production in order to avoid curtailments and mitigate the mismatch between
48 production and demand [9]. Furthermore, storage systems provide ancillary services to the grid, including black start
49 and voltage support. Overall, it can be concluded that the ongoing energy transition has altered the conventional,
50 passive, fuel-based power grid into an active, controllable, bidirectional smart grid. This means that the respective
51 infrastructures need to be modified accordingly. According to the guidelines of certain research and innovation
52 projects, it would be more efficient to have Direct Current (DC) lines in grids with high DC penetration, such as solar
53 panels, electric vehicles (EVs), data centres, etc. [10]. On the other hand, according to manufacturers, it is mandatory
54 to upgrade the protection schemes of the distribution network [11].

55 1.2 Solid-state transformers and inductive power transfer

56 However, nowadays, most attention is paid to substituting the grid's conventional transformers with devices more
57 suitable for the requirements of smart grids. Perhaps the most researched solution is the Solid-State Transformer
58 (SST) [12], which is also the main focus of this study. The basic concept of an SST replacing the conventional
59 transformer is presented in Fig. 1.

60

61 **Fig. 1.** Basic concept of an SST (top), replacing a conventional transformer (bottom).

62 The SST is a power electronics device that usually comprises three stages: i) the conversion of Medium Voltage
63 Alternating Current (MVAC) into Medium Voltage Direct Current (MVDC), ii) the conversion of MVDC into Low
64 Voltage Direct Current (LVDC), which usually happens through a medium or high-frequency transformer, and iii)
65 the conversion of LVDC into Low Voltage Alternating Current (LVAC) [13]. This architecture is more complex than
66 that of the conventional transformer and has also higher cost and maintenance requirements. Yet, it is considered to
67 be more advanced as it is more controllable, modular and can even provide branches for DC grids [14].

68 The SST can inhibit the propagation of disturbances and harmonics, regulate voltage and frequency levels, control
69 reactive power, perform fault management, etc. Therefore, it can facilitate the provision of ancillary services to the
70 main grid operator, the connection of weak grids or even the connection of hybrid AC/DC grids. Although researchers
71 acknowledge that SSTs cannot fully replace conventional transformers, the purpose is to install them strategically in
72 specific distribution lines where their effect can be maximized. Their existing and envisioned applications include
73 railways, data centres, smart grids, offshore WFs, utility-scale Photovoltaic (PV) plants, EVs charging stations,
74 maritime and aerospace sectors, storage plants and Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) [10,12,15]. For the
75 purposes of research and development, a variety of projects, such as TIGON [16] and HEART [17], as well as

76 manufacturers, such as Hitachi Energy [18], SIEMENS [19] and EFACEC [20] have developed SSTs. However,
77 since this is a relatively new technology, the developed SSTs do not have a common architecture, nor do they operate
78 at the same voltage and frequency levels. For example, there are SSTs where the DC/DC conversion is designed at
79 20 kHz while in other design cases the same conversion is designed at 50 kHz [12]. This is a typical trade-off of
80 emerging technologies and is expected to be mitigated in the course of time, as the concept of SSTs matures.

81 One of the main open discussion points regarding SST architectures is the design of the middle stage, where the
82 conversion from MVDC to LVDC happens, i.e., the medium or high-frequency transformer. The design, including
83 the core material, the geometry, the insulation and the thermal management are important when it comes to the power
84 loss density, operating temperatures capability and magnetic and electric parasitic effects. The core material needs to
85 be a soft magnetic material such as ferrite, amorphous alloy or nanocrystalline, according to Shamshuddin et al. [21]
86 and She et al. [22]. Besides the core material, core geometry is also an important factor to decide the compact design,
87 heat dissipation and achievable voltage transfer ratios. Several different core geometries are reported in the literature,
88 namely: i) core type, ii) shell type, iii) matrix type, iv) Co-axial Winding Type (CWT) and v) Inductive Power
89 Transfer (IPT) type [23]. Although the core and shell types are the most common ones, the IPT type has gained
90 attention over the past few years as its innovative design expands the typical converter's capabilities, enhancing
91 aspects related to safety and convenience. For instance, this technology enables the wireless charging of EVs, in the
92 case where half of the SST is placed in the EV and the other half is placed outside and underneath the EV, without
93 the interaction of the driver by eliminating the charging cables [24,25]. The ascending utilization of IPT systems is
94 one of the main motives behind this study.

95 1.3 Brief literature review on thermal management of SSTs - IPT

96 Usually, transformers operate inside enclosures that are filled with the dielectric liquid of sufficient insulation
97 properties [26,27]. However, this may lead to the development of increased temperatures causing deterioration of the
98 transformer's components due to the development of thermal stresses. To optimize the lifetime, reliability and loading
99 capacity of transformers, the thermal aspects of both conventional [26–32] as well as solid-state transformers [33–
100 41], are being exploited in several recent studies by employing computational approaches, aiming to develop
101 advanced, coupled electromagnetic-thermal simulation models. Below, the recent advancements regarding the
102 simulation strategies relevant to the thermal management of solid-state transformers are presented. Mogorovic et al.
103 [33] developed a novel algorithm for the design of SSTs, including the calculation of losses, magnetic energy and
104 hot-spot temperatures. According to the developed algorithm, a shell type 100 kW, 10 kHz prototype was developed
105 and tested, verifying the theoretical design which was estimated to reach a maximum temperature equal to 125 °C.
106 Tian et al. [34] proposed a coupled, semi-numerical model to analyse the thermal behaviour of a medium-frequency,
107 oil natural air natural (ONAN) core-type transformer. Wang et al. [35] studied the electric stress and dielectric
108 breakdown characteristics of a 166 kW SST for frequencies ranging from 0.5 up to 8 kHz. They examined the effect
109 of frequency and temperature on the breakdown strength of epoxy resin insulation by conducting both 2-D-FEM
110 simulations and experiments, concluding that the breakdown strength of the epoxy is reduced as the frequency and
111 temperature increase. They considered the effect of temperatures up to 120 °C and frequencies, up to 8 kHz and
112 attributed the resulting breakdown strength to the glass transition of epoxy resin. Beheshtaein et al. [36] investigated
113 the operation of a 667 kW SiC MOSFET-based, shell-type, SST operating at 13 kV to 7.2 kV with frequency equal
114 to 20 kHz through the conduction of simulation using ANSYS. They demonstrated that by utilising a hybrid, forced
115 air-cooling and water-cooling system, the efficiency of the transformer may reach 99.95%. Ichou et al. [37],
116 investigated the thermal behaviour of an innovative SST whose core is made of grain-oriented electrical steel
117 (GOES). The SST uses a forced air-cooling system and operates at 350 V, 2 kHz. The prototype was constructed and
118 tested and according to the experimental results, it reaches temperatures equal to 320 °C, 160 °C and 150 °C in the
119 core, high and low voltage windings, respectively. Bahmani [39] proposed a design and optimization methodology

of an SST taking into consideration the inductance of the transformer, core and windings losses mitigation, thermal management and isolation requirements. For this purpose, several frequency-dependent expressions were examined and derived either analytically or based on finite element analysis (FEA) simulations. Using the proposed design method, two down-scaled prototype transformers, operating at 50 kW, 5 kHz, were designed, manufactured and tested. According to the results, the nanocrystalline-based prototype reached an efficiency of 99.66%, whereas the ferrite-based prototype showed a measured efficiency of 99.58%, which were almost identical to the theoretically predicted values. Finally, Stadler [38] studied the AC resistance and losses of an SST's litz wire windings using FEM. The simulations consider a wide range of frequencies and highlight the effect of the frequency on the winding resistance, especially when the frequency exceeds 10 kHz. The simulation results were verified with experimental results from four different types of litz wire.

From the brief literature review on the thermal management of SSTs and conventional transformers, it can be concluded that the thermal aspects have been adequately studied in the literature. On the other hand, the evaluation of the IPT integration in relevant studies is still considerably underexplored as the available research works concentrate on the electromagnetic characteristics. For example, in [42] the performance of an IPT for electric vehicle wireless charging applications was studied through a novel simulation model combining an electrical circuit with a nonlinear FE model using ANSYS. Haque et al. [43] compared the performance of 22 kHz and 85 kHz, 50 kW wireless charging systems for electric vehicles, using Si and SiC switches. The results indicated that the system efficiency at 85 kHz can be increased by 21 % compared to 22 kHz operation by using a SiC MOSFET converter. Cervero et al. [44] have developed a 50 kW, 2.2 kV SST prototype with an IPT, in the context of the FST project which aims to derive a Unified Power Flow Controller (UPFC) to be installed in a transmission power line located in Bescanó-Sentmenat, Spain.

Evidently, it can be concluded that although the thermal aspects of the usual core or shell-type SSTs, whether they utilize a forced cooling system or not, have been studied by various researchers, on the contrary, the thermal aspects of SSTs with IPT are still considerably underexplored since, so far, the focus is given to their electric properties. Therefore, this paper aims to expand the existing literature by investigating the heat transfer mechanisms of a novel IPT which is designed to operate at 1.5 kV / 0.4 kV with power equal to 50 kW and frequency equal to 50 kHz, submerged in a dielectric fluid. This SST is designed and shall be further developed in the context of SSTAR, a Horizon Europe project [45]. A two-way coupled electromagnetic-thermal model is established which is used to calculate the temperature distribution of the IPT components based on the electromagnetic losses. The developed model is later used to conduct a parametric investigation on the effect of operating frequency and dielectric gap between high and low voltage windings. The obtained results illustrate for the first time, the heat transfer mechanisms of a novel inductive power-transfer system and highlight some guidelines for the optimal design of the module that could help towards their market uptake, ultimately supporting the needs of the current energy transition.

2 Materials and methods

This section describes the modeling of the SST geometry and the setup of the simulation model. The geometry of the model is constructed using CAD tools and the electromagnetic-thermal coupling scheme is developed and discussed. Since the SSTAR is an on-going research project, a conceptual version of the IPT module has been concluded at this stage. The simulation model is developed using ANSYS Maxwell and Icepak software [46].

2.1 Geometry of the IPT module

The simplified geometry of the newly introduced transformer is depicted in Fig. 2. The geometry of the model consists of the dielectric fluid, the magnetic core, the aluminum shield and the Litz windings, submerged in the dielectric fluid. Windings are composed of round copper Litz wires in a typical bundle-type configuration [47]. Each

162 Litz bundle is modelled as a single homogenized object with the same outer diameter leading to the reduction of the
 163 computational cost [48].

164
 165 **Fig. 2.** Layout and basic dimensions of the IPT module with the main components being: (1) dielectric fluid, (2)
 166 primary shield, (3) secondary shield, (4) low voltage winding, (5) secondary core, (6) high voltage winding, (7)
 167 primary core. (a) Isometric view, (b) isometric - top section view, (c) isometric – front section view, (d) top section
 168 with main in-plane dimensions and (e) front section view with main out-of-plane dimensions.

169 The basic dimensions of the system are given in Table 1. The thickness of the tank walls is equal to 5 mm.

170 Table 1. Main dimensions of the IPT module (all dimensions in mm).

l_1	l_2	l_3	h_1	h_2	h_3	t_1	t_2	t_3	w	R
250	360	460	50	80	180	5	5	20	50	60

171 2.2 Heat transfer model and coupling scheme

172 During operation, IPT generates heat due to the induction of an electromagnetic field between its primary and
 173 secondary windings resulting in power loss. The thermal energy generated should be dissipated to avoid damage to
 174 the transformer due to the developed thermal stresses. Understanding the natural thermal flow mechanisms of the
 175 IPT is crucial in comprehending heat transfer and ensuring reliable and efficient operation. Heat is generated by the

176 core and windings in the IPT, and it is mainly conducted through the shields of the primary and secondary
 177 components. The uneven heat generation between primary and secondary parts results in the formation of localized
 178 hot spots [49,50]. The total thermal energy produced is transferred by convection through the dielectric fluid and then
 179 dispersed into the environment mainly by conduction through the walls of the tank. Additionally, the primary and
 180 secondary shield walls and tank walls absorb and emit thermal energy in the form of electromagnetic waves. This
 181 thermal radiation contributes to the heat transfer process. The natural thermal flow mechanisms can be seen in Fig.
 182 3.

183
 184 **Fig. 3.** Deciphering the heat dissipation in Inductive Power Transfer. Core and litz-wire generated heat conducts
 185 through primary and secondary shields, leading to local hotspots. Thermal energy is channeled via convection in the
 186 dielectric fluid and radiated through shield and tank walls, enhancing heat transfer dynamics.

187 The modelling approach is based on the interaction and transfer of data between two main models: the
 188 electromagnetic and the thermal one [49]. The stray losses of the electromagnetic model are calculated to obtain the
 189 heat source which is used by the thermal model [51]. The equations governing the 3-D coupled electromagnetic-
 190 thermal-fluid analysis are described below. In the magnetic field analysis, the T- Ω method [52] is used to compute
 191 the stray losses of the transformer. Using Maxwell's equation and based on the Coulomb gauge, the stray losses of
 192 the transformer, which include eddy current losses and hysteresis losses, can be computed:

$$\nabla \times \frac{1}{\sigma} \nabla \times \mathbf{T} + \frac{\partial}{\partial t} [\mu_e (\mathbf{T} - \Delta \Omega)] = 0, \quad (11)$$

193 where: (\mathbf{T}) is the electric vector potential, (Ω) the magnetic scalar potential, (μ_e) the permeability and (σ) the
 194 conductivity. The energy equation in non-eddy current regions which include the magnetic core, the non-conductive
 195 parts and the current source regions is formulated as

$$\nabla \cdot [\mu_e (-\nabla \Omega) + H_s] = 0, \quad (22)$$

196 where: (H_s) is the magnetic field. The heat transfer analysis at the boundaries is conducted using the heat transfer
 197 equation by assuming stationary fluid:

$$\frac{\partial(\rho T)}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \nabla T \right) + S, \quad (33)$$

198 where: (c_p) is the specific heat capacity, (ρ) the density, (λ) the heat transfer coefficient, (S) the source term and
 199 (T) the temperature. The transformer's internal heat transfer coefficient is determined by dividing the heat flux by
 200 the temperature difference between the dielectric fluid and solid components. Afterwards, the convection heat transfer
 201 coefficients are incorporated into the magnetic-thermal coupling analysis. When the transformer is in steady-state
 202 operation, the heat transfer equation and boundary condition is established, with (λ_{xx}), (λ_{yy}), and (λ_{zz}) representing
 203 the thermal conductivities along the (x), (y), and (z) directions, respectively, expressed as [53]:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\lambda_x \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\lambda_y \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\lambda_z \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right) = -q(x, y, z), \quad (44)$$

204 and

$$q_w = -\lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial n} = -\lambda (n \cdot \nabla T) = - \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{xx} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_{zz} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x} n_x \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial y} n_y \\ \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} n_z \end{bmatrix}, \quad (55)$$

205 where (q) is the power loss. The stray losses in the metallic parts of the transformer include eddy current losses and
 206 hysteresis losses. The stray loss distributions derived from the electromagnetic analysis are applied as the boundary
 207 conditions for the thermal analysis in order to calculate the temperature distribution through the solution of the heat
 208 transfer equation. The system of the described equations is solved using ANSYS Maxwell-Icepak software to
 209 calculate the magnetic and thermal characteristics. The coupling scheme is presented in Fig. 4.

210

211 **Fig. 4.** Integrating electromagnetic and thermal solutions in a coupled scheme. Eddy current and hysteresis losses
 212 serve as thermal analysis boundaries, enabling ANSYS Maxwell-Icepak to compute magnetic-thermal interplay and
 213 temperature distribution via coupled equations.

214 2.3 Utilised materials

215 The selected materials are Copper 1650 and Copper 330 for the low voltage and high voltage winding respectively,
 216 ferrite F-867 for the primary and secondary core, and aluminium 6061 for the primary and secondary shield. For the
 217 electromagnetic analysis, the oil volume considered is modelled as an inductive medium, while for thermal analysis,
 218 it is modelled as a convective medium. The thermal properties of the dielectric fluid used in the simulations are taken
 219 from [26] while the electromagnetic properties are taken from [54]. The properties of the IPT components, including

220 the dielectric fluid, are presented in Table 2. Each temperature-dependent property taken from published experimental
 221 results is given at the reference temperature along with the related reference.

222 In the context of the electromagnetic Maxwell solution, the B-H and B-P curves elucidate the magnetic characteristics
 223 of a ferrite core. The B-H curve delineates the nonlinear relationship between magnetic flux density (B) and magnetic
 224 field strength (H) within the core. As H increases, B initially rises proportionally, but eventually saturates, indicating
 225 the point at which the core's magnetic domains become fully aligned. Simultaneously, the B-P curve portrays the
 226 core's magnetic polarization (P) in response to H, starting linearly and transitioning into saturation as alignment
 227 progresses. These curves play a pivotal role in modelling the core's magnetic behaviour, guiding the design and
 228 analysis of electromagnetic systems by offering insights into saturation effects and magnetic performance across
 229 varying field strengths. In the present study the curves are adopted from [55].

230 Table 2. Properties of the components of the IPT module.

Component	ELECTROMAGNETIC		THERMAL	
	Property	Value	Property	Value
Low Voltage Winding & High Voltage Winding	Relative Permittivity	1	Thermal Conductivity	$8.64 \cdot 10^{-5}(T - 20)^2 - 0.104(T - 20) + 404.18$ [W/m°C] [26]
	Relative Permeability	0.9999		
	Bulk Conductivity	58×10^6 [Siemens/m] @ T_{ref} Exp. Curve [56]	Mass Density	8,933 [kg/m ³]
	Loss Tangent	0		
	Composition	Litz Wire	Specific Heat	$-3.2 \cdot 10^{-4}(T - 20)^2 + 0.221(T - 20) + 376.98$ [J/Kg°C] [26]
	Wire Type	Round		
	Strand Number	1,650 & 330	Expansion Coefficient	$1.77 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [1/°C]
	Wire Diameter	0.16 mm		Type
Primary Core & Secondary Core	Relative Permittivity	12	Thermal Conductivity	4 [W/m°C]
	Relative Permeability	B-H Curve [55]		
	Bulk Conductivity	0.15 [Siemens/m]	Mass Density	4,600 [kg/m ³]
	Loss Tangent	0		
	Core Loss Model	B-P curve [55]	Specific Heat	$-2.91 \cdot 10^{-4}(T - 20)^2 + 0.522(T - 20) + 431.88$ [J/Kg°C] [26]
Composition	Solid	Expansion Coefficient		10^{-5} [1/°C]
Primary Shield & Secondary Shield	Relative Permittivity	1	Thermal Conductivity	173 [W/m°C] @ T_{ref} Exp. Curve [57]
	Relative Permeability	1.000021		
	Bulk Conductivity	38,000,000 [Siemens/m] @ T_{ref} [56]	Mass Density	2,689 [kg/m ³]
	Loss Tangent	0		
	Composition	Solid	Expansion Coefficient	$2.33 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [1/°C]
		Type		Solid
Dielectric Fluid	Relative Permittivity	3	Thermal Conductivity	0.11 [W/m°C] @ T_{ref} Exp. Curve [26]
	Relative Permeability	2.5		
	Bulk Conductivity	$3 \cdot 10^{-7}$ [Siemens/m]	Mass Density	900 [kg/m ³] @ T_{ref} Exp. Curve [26]
	Dielectric Loss tan	0.015		
		Specific Heat	1740 [J/kg°C] @ T_{ref} Exp. Curve [26]	
			Thermal Expansion Coefficient	0.000675 [1/°C]

Magnetic Loss tan	0.001	Dynamic Viscosity	0.061 [Pa s] @T _{ref} Exp. Curve [26]
Composition	Solid	Thermal Diffusivity	8.74 10 ⁻⁵ [m ² /s]
		Molecular Mass	0.452 [kg/mol]
		Type	Fluid

231 2.4 Excitations

232 The eddy current analysis for the electromagnetic model is carried out in Ansys Maxwell by selecting the eddy current
 233 solution type, which computes steady-state, time-varying (AC) magnetic fields at a given frequency in the frequency
 234 domain. Several assumptions are made; i.e. that all objects are stationary and the source of the static magnetic field
 235 is a sinusoidal AC (peak) in the conductors, while time-varying external magnetic fields are neglected. The quantities
 236 solved are the magnetic field and the magnetic scalar potential, while the density and magnetic flux density can be
 237 calculated from (H_s). The eddy current solution involves natural boundaries at the interfaces between objects, which
 238 ensures that the (H_s) field remains continuous across these boundaries. The outer boundaries, on the other hand, are
 239 treated as Neumann conditions. The surfaces of the dielectric fluid act as insulating boundaries. The impact of these
 240 boundaries on the results is minimal since the isolation distances between the coils are adequate. The excitations
 241 defined in the electromagnetic model are presented in Table 3.

242 Table 3. Excitations used in the electromagnetic model.

Assignment	Excitations	Properties	Value / Unit
Primary HV Windings	Coil Terminal - Stranded	Number of Conductors	20
		Direction	Point Out of Terminal
		Winding Type	Current
		Current	31.25 A
		No of Parallel Branches	1
		Phase	0°
Secondary LV Windings	Coil Terminal - Stranded	Number of Conductors	5
		Direction	Point Into Terminal
		Winding Type	Current
		Current	118.75 A
		No of Parallel Branches	1
		Phase	45°

243

244 2.5 Computational mesh

245 The computational mesh utilized in the simulation is a hybrid one, comprised of both tetrahedral and hexahedral
 246 elements. An adaptive remeshing method was applied during the solution in the electromagnetic analysis to refine
 247 the mesh at the regions of interests. The adaptive remeshing algorithm utilizes hexahedral elements near the
 248 transformer's components, while tetrahedral elements are used close to the tank walls. Fig. 5 shows three section
 249 views of the geometry (the planes coincide at the center of gravity) where hexahedral elements are observed. Besides
 250 the adaptive remeshing, a mesh independence study was conducted to determine the initial maximum element size
 251 for each component in order to guarantee accurate results converge. Table 3 presents the results of the mesh-
 252 independence study. The final mesh consists of approximately 1 million cells and it corresponds to the solution
 253 obtained from the third run (Table 3).

254

255

Table 3. Results of mesh independence study.

Run 1			Run 2			Run 3			Run 4		
# El.	q_t (W)	T_m (°C)	# El.	q_t (W)	T_m (°C)	# El.	q (W)	T_m (°C)	# El.	q_t (W)	T_m (°C)
354335	705.33	192.72	669759	707.03	192.95	911083	707.69	193.05	1311278	708.03	193.08
Percentage difference			0.24			0.09			0.05		

Fig. 5. Computational mesh of the model. (a) x-z section, (b) x-y section, (c) y-z section.

3 Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results of the simulations. Initially, the results presented correspond to the nominal operating conditions that the IPT module is designed for (50 kHz, 50 mm dielectric gap). The contour plots of the magnetic flux density, power loss and temperature are plotted and discussed at this operating point. In this way, the fundamental aspects of the heat transfer mechanisms in the module are assessed. Besides 2-D contour plots, the temperature distribution at characteristic locations of the module is plotted, revealing the main differences regarding temperature levels between primary and secondary components. Later on, the results of the parametric investigation are presented. The parameters of interest are the operating frequency, which ranges between 25 and 100 kHz with a 25 kHz step, and the dielectric gap which is tested at 25 mm, 50 mm and 100 mm.

The magnetic flux density within the cores of the inductive power transformer serves as a pivotal determinant of its magnetic performance and is presented in Fig. 6. Specifically, the regions where the litz wires are placed emerge as sites of maximum flux density concentration. These Litz wires, acting as pathways for both primary and secondary currents, engender magnetic fields that effectively permeate the adjacent ferrite cores. Consequently, the magnetic flux lines, induced by the current flowing through the Litz wires, peak in density precisely at these designated points. Intriguingly, the secondary ferrite core showcases a concentration of flux density at lower values in comparison to the primary core. This discrepancy in flux distribution is attributed to varying turn ratios and coupling coefficients between primary and secondary windings, influencing the magnetic interactions within the two cores.

Fig. 6. Magnetic field developed in the IPT module.

Fig. 7 presents the contour plots of power losses and temperature fields at the components of the IPT module. The electromagnetic loss distribution in the inductive power transformer reveals distinct characteristics between the primary transmitter and the secondary receiver. Notably, the secondary receiver demonstrates a lower power loss distribution, resulting in reduced temperatures within its structural components. This discrepancy can be attributed to the diminished mutual inductance between the coils, a consequence of the dielectric gap and the counteraction of magnetic fields induced by eddy currents on the aluminum shield. Additionally, fluid loss density variations arise due to displacement currents, with higher values observed in the regions between windings. Litz wires, known for their multistrand construction, are employed to mitigate skin and proximity effects, reducing the resistance of the windings and consequently minimizing ohmic losses. However, even with the use of Litz wires, ohmic losses still occur due to the inherent resistance of the wire material. Notably, the inner layers of the wire exhibit a more pronounced loss distribution owing to escalated magnetic flux linkage and heightened magnetic induction within these internal wire layers. This heightened induction induces more substantial eddy currents within the inner layers, surpassing those in the outer layers. These additional eddy currents contribute to an elevation in resistance, consequently resulting in an augmented prevalence of ohmic losses within the inner layers of the Litz wires. The maximum value of power loss in the cores equals $9.21E10^5$ W/m³ while the windings' maximum power loss value equals $5.15E10^6$ W/m³. The total windings loss is calculated at approximately 0.25 kW while the total core loss is 0.5 kW.

Shifting to the thermal aspects, the analysis indicates higher maximum temperatures in the primary structures of the IPT compared to the secondary ones. This outcome aligns with expectations, given the inductive efficiency between the transmitter and receiver, leading to greater electromagnetic loss in the transmitting primary coil due to the gap. The highest temperature recorded in the primary components is 218 °C. Notably, the inner winding area exhibits the highest temperatures, in accordance with the concentration of thermal energy generated and conducted by copper wires. Conversely, the outer winding regions facilitate outward heat dissipation, mitigating heat concentration. The temperature distribution within the ferrite core of the inductive power transformer mirrors that of the coil, with peak temperatures concentrated at the region where the windings are placed. Contrasting this, the temperature distribution on the aluminium shielding plate primarily relies on thermal diffusion mechanisms rather than intrinsic loss density. Concerning the temperature distribution of the dielectric fluid, its main heat transfer mechanisms are convective heat exchange between the structural components and the fluid itself, and the natural convective heat exchange between the outer tank surface containing the fluid and the air surrounding the tank. These findings underscore the intricate interplay between electromagnetic and thermal factors, emphasizing the need for meticulous design considerations to optimize the performance and thermal management of inductive power transfer systems.

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311 **Fig. 7.** Simulation results at the nominal operating point (50 kHz, 50 mm): (a) cores power loss density, (b) cores
 312 temperature distribution, (c) windings power loss density, (d) windings temperature distribution, (e) dielectric fluid
 313 loss density, (f) dielectric fluid temperature distribution.

314 Fig 8. presents the temperature distribution along the x-direction at three y-positions of the primary and secondary
 315 cores ($z=0$ m, $z=0.1$ m, $z=-0.1$ m). A temperature difference of approximately 30 °C exists between the primary and
 316 secondary cores. The high-temperature region in the cores is located at the winding's footprint, consistent with the
 317 power loss field. In fact, an almost uniform temperature distribution is obtained at the regions which overlap with the
 318 windings ($z=\pm 0.1$ m). On the contrary, at $z=0$ the temperature decreases approximately 7 °C as approaching to the
 319 centreline of the core.

Fig. 8. Temperature distribution at three indicative positions of the IPT's cores. (a) Primary core, (b) secondary core.

It becomes evident that the temperature profile is intricately influenced by the thermal conductivity and heat capacity characteristics of the materials employed. The dissipation of heat within the system occurs in a manner that fosters a uniform concentration of thermal energy across both the copper windings and the ferrite core. The materials' thermal conductivity dictates the rate at which heat is transferred within the transformer, ensuring efficient conduction of thermal energy. Simultaneously, the heat capacity of these materials governs their ability to absorb and store heat, modulating the overall thermal response of the system. The uniform distribution of heat in the copper windings and ferrite core is vital in sustaining optimal operating temperatures, preventing localized hotspots that could compromise the transformer's integrity, and underscores the significance of selecting materials with well-matched thermal properties to uphold efficient and reliable performance under varying load conditions.

Finally, Figs. 9, 10 illustrate the effect of the operating frequency on the power loss and temperature levels, considering three cases of dielectric gap (25 mm, 50 mm, 100 mm). In the analysis of the inductive power transfer systems, these plots reveal clear relationships between key parameters and electromagnetic losses and temperatures. It is evident that core losses increase with a cubic trend with higher frequencies and reduced primary-secondary core gaps, even though the gap dependency becomes negligible as the gap increases. For instance, when (h_1) increases from 25 mm to 50 mm, core loss decreases by a factor of approximately 1.66, but when the gap is doubled again to 100 mm, core loss remains independent. The rise in frequency intensifies eddy current losses within the core material, while minimizing the core gap enhances magnetic coupling and flux linkage, intensifying magnetic energy dissipation. In contrast, winding losses rise with frequency due to skin and proximity effects, yet they remain unaffected by core gap variations. This observation underscores the complex interplay between these factors, necessitating a holistic design approach for optimizing transformer efficiency and performance.

Turning to the thermal behaviour, the amplified electromagnetic losses hold significant implications for transformer temperature. The elevated core losses resulting from increased frequency and decreased core gap lead to higher heat generation within the transformer, contributing to an overall rise in mean temperature. Moreover, as core losses intensify, the maximum temperature reached by the transformer also increases linearly. The cumulative impact of these increased losses emphasizes the vital role of thermal management strategies to mitigate excessive temperature rise, prevent insulation degradation, and ensure the reliable operation and longevity of the inductive power transformer in demanding operational conditions.

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Fig. 9 Power loss versus operating frequency at three values of the dielectric gap. (a) Cores loss, (b) windings loss.

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Fig. 9 Temperature versus operating frequency at three values of the dielectric gap. (a) Mean value, (b) maximum value.

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4 Conclusions

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This paper presents the heat transfer mechanisms and the temperature fields developed in an innovative SST incorporating an IPT system. The IPT system is designed to operate at 1.5 kV / 0.4 kV with power equal to 50 kW and frequency equal to 50 kHz and shall be manufactured in the context of SSTAR, a Horizon Europe project. The transformer is considered immersed in a stationary dielectric fluid which serves as a medium for convection and naturally transfers thermal energy to the surrounding environment.

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For the purpose of this study, the thermal analysis is conducted through a two-way coupled electromagnetic-thermal finite element simulation model, using the commercial software ANSYS in order to assess the heat transfer mechanisms of the IPT module. The power loss calculated from the electromagnetic model was applied as a heat source to the thermal model in order to calculate the temperature distribution on the parts of the transformer and modify accordingly the temperature-dependent electromagnetic properties.

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The total power loss calculated at the nominal operation of the module (50 kHz, 50 mm gap) was in the order of 0.5 kW and the maximum temperature was in the order of 218 °C. The results indicate that the maximum power loss and consequently temperature is located at the windings. The temperature distribution at the windings is uniform.

368 Following this, the cores exhibit also increased temperatures. The distribution is uniform at the regions of the cores
369 adjacent to the windings, while it decreases approximately 10 °C at the inner regions. In addition, the primary
370 components of the module exhibit increased properties compared to the secondary ones by approximately 10 °C.

371 To assess the effect of operating frequency and dielectric gap on the power loss and temperature levels, a parametric
372 analysis was conducted. The results highlighted the cubic law increase of power loss of both the cores and the
373 windings with respect to the frequency while on the contrary, the effect of the gap was negligible. Only in the case
374 of the increase of the gap from 25 mm to 100 mm, an increase at the power loss by a factor of 1.66 was obtained.

375 The preliminary results indicate that the temperature levels at the components of the transformer are increased, which
376 is attributed to the absence of a forced cooling system which is expected to be included in later stages of this project.
377 In addition, the results highlight the need to perform thermal-structural simulations in order to calculate the resulting
378 strain fields due to the developed thermal stresses and verify the structural integrity of the transformer. Finally, the
379 experimental verification of the results is expected to be tracked in the context of the project after the prototype
380 manufacturing.

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